

STUDY ON BONDING STRENGTH OF BAMBOO/BAMBOO UNIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATE WITH UF AND PF-EFFECT OF PRESSING TIME ON ADHESIVE BONDING STRENGTH

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Abstract

Bamboo has gain attention due to its unique functionally graded microstructure and excellent mechanical properties. Following our previous studies on mechanical (bending and compression) and physical properties of Beting bamboo (*Gigantochloa levis*), the bonding strength properties of bamboo/bamboo and have been evaluated prior to fabrication of bamboo-aluminum sandwich composites. Single lap joint shear test were performed to evaluate the bond strength of the laminar interfaces. Two types of adhesives -Phenol formaldehyde (PF) and Urea Formaldehyde (UF) is used to bond bamboo/bamboo laminate.

1 Introduction

Malaysia is blessed with abundant resources of bamboo species. Bamboo has been made into an extended diversity of non structural products ranging from domestic household products to industrial applications. In Asian countries, bamboo is commonly available raw materials for construction. There are many houses in Thailand and Vietnam made entirely from bamboo In recent decades, bamboo has attracted more attention as an alternative to timber due to its short (3-5) years rotation and favorable mechanical properties for solid bamboo and also medium density fiberboard and pulp and paper products [1-2]. Bamboo not only can be used in fiber form, but also in form of splits, strips or round form application. Various studies have been conducted to characterize the mechanical properties of bamboo in various forms and suitability of bamboo for different applications.

Reformed bamboo strips are more convenient for various engineering applications than the

natural form bamboo. Based on our preliminary study of bamboo (*G. levis*) it is found that bamboo slabs have favorable physical and mechanical properties. Reformed bamboo slabs can be easily manipulated to construct sandwich structure with combination of other material such as aluminum sheet. Combination of commonly available bamboo and other more superior material is very promising as not only the demand for the use of lighter and stronger sandwich structure continue to grow, but also due to the reputation of bamboo as green and eco friendly materials. Bamboo is not only has high specific strength and modulus, but also high yield over time and degradable.

1.1 Urea Formaldehyde and Phenol formaldehyde Resin

Urea formaldehyde resin is a thermosetting resin and consists of linear or branched oligomers and polymers always admixed with some amounts of monomers. After hardening, UF resins consist of insoluble, three dimensional networks that cannot be melted or thermoformed again. The following chemical species are present in UF resins; free formaldehyde, monomeric methylol groups, oligomeric methylol groups and molecules with higher molar masses [3]

Phenol formaldehyde is consists of two building blocks; phenol and formaldehyde. In the PF solution, phenol and formaldehyde are available at a molar ratio of about 2.2. Most of the formaldehyde will be bonded permanently within the three dimensional cross linking PF network [4]

Property	UF	PF
Price	Low	Medium
Necessary hardening temperature	Low	High
Efficiency	Low	Medium-High
Manipulation	Easy	Easy
Resistance against boiling water	No	High

Table 1: Evaluation of UF and PF with regard to various parameters

During the curing process a three dimensional network is formed. Urea formaldehyde resins differ from other formaldehyde resin such as Phenol formaldehyde resin due to their high reactivity and hence short hot press time is achievable. However, phenol formaldehyde is favorable in terms of very low formaldehyde in service after hardening. Table 1 summarize the evaluation of Urea formaldehyde and Phenol formaldehyde with regard to various parameters [5]

In this study prior to fabrication of bamboo aluminum sandwich composites, the adhesive shear strength between bamboo and bamboo interface is determined at different parameters. These parameters are different types of resins (Urea Formaldehyde and Phenol Formaldehyde) and different pressing time (2 to 10 minutes).

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Beting bamboo (*G. levis*) is obtained in bulk from State of Pahang, Malaysia. Bamboos are air dried and machined using one side Makita planer to produce flat planed surface

2.2 Adhesives

To study the shear strength of bamboo/bamboo, two different types of adhesives; Phenol formaldehyde and Urea Formaldehyde (supplied by Malayan Adhesive Chemicals Company Ltd) are used. Table 2 shows the characteristics of adhesives used in this study as provided by the supplier

Adhesives	pH at 30°C	Viscosity in poise at 30°C	Specific gravity at 30°C	Free formaldehyde in % at 25°C	Non volatile content in % (3 hrs)
Urea formaldehyde	7.86	1.40	1.194	0.80	49.2 (at 105°C)
Phenol formaldehyde	12.49	0.54	1.186	-	40.6 (at 135°C)

Table 2: Characteristics of adhesives used (UF and PF) as provided by the supplier

Figure 1: Samples dimensions for single lap shear test

3 Experimental Procedures

The shear samples are produced by pressing the bamboo slabs (inner-inner) using laboratory hot press at 3 different pressing time (2, 5 and 10) minutes at pressure of 50kg/cm³ using two different adhesives; PF and UF at temperature 145-150°C. Prior to that, PF and UF are applied using hand brush to produce thin single glue-line at only one (inner surface) side of the bamboo slab. Bamboo slabs are lay-up in unidirectional configuration (Bamboo/0°/0°/Bamboo). Figure 1 shows the samples for lap shear test. The dimension of the sample is based on the method suggested by previous work by Zhang et.al [6] with some modifications. The loading tension speed is 5mm/min. The loading is carried out until a break or separation occurred. Observed load F_{max} , bonding area (A, mm²) and shear strength σ_s are calculated as follows

$$\sigma_s = F_{max}/A \text{ (N/mm}^2\text{)}$$

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Shear Strength of UF and PF bonded bamboo laminate

Bonding shear strength test was conducted after exposure to 20°C ±3°C and 65±5% humidity for approximately 2 weeks. 142 test samples (min 17 samples for 3 different processing temperatures for both PF and UF adhesives are prepared. Three different processing temperatures are chosen: 2, 5 and 10 minutes. The moisture content of samples prior to testing is 8-10%. For bamboo laminated with Phenol formaldehyde, the average shear strength for each parameter (2, 5 and 10 minutes) is 4.09, 5.36 and 5.81 MPa respectively. For bamboo laminated with Urea formaldehyde, the average

shear strength is 3.80, 6.13 and 6.11 MPa respectively. The result is shown in the graph at figure 2.

From the experiment, it is found that the average shear strength tend to increase when the pressing time is increased during samples preparation. With short press time at 140°C, low lap joint shear strength was observed with almost of the samples failed at adhesive bond line. For samples bonded with Urea formaldehyde, the highest average shear strength is recorded for samples pressed at 5 minutes while for samples bonded with Phenol formaldehyde, the samples pressed at 10 minutes showed the highest average shear strength. The shear strength of adhesive increased by 60% and 42% for both Urea formaldehyde and Phenol formaldehyde respectively when press time increased from 2 minutes to 10 minutes.

From ANOVA statistical analysis, there is a significance difference between means of shear strength of bamboo laminated with Urea formaldehyde and Phenol formaldehyde when tested at 95% confidence interval (P<0.05). However, the shear strength of both UF and PF for samples pressed at 5 and 10 minutes respectively are not significantly difference when analysed using Tukey Multiple Comparison at 95% confidence interval.

For UF resins, the adhesive strength slightly reduced when samples pressed at longer pressing time than 5 minutes. UF resins are different from PF resins due to high reactivity, hence strong adhesive bonding strength is achievable at lower pressing time compared to PF resin. This is one of the disadvantages of PF resins compared to UF resins. However, complete resistance to hydrolysis of the C-C bond between the aromatic nucleus and the methylene bridge of PF resins is favorable for its use exterior weather conditions [3]

Figure 2: Adhesive shear strength of Urea formaldehyde (UF) and Phenol formaldehyde (PF) pressed at different pressing time (2-5 minutes). Bar represent standard deviation. Figure on right side represent scattered individual plot of shear strength of each samples with interval bar.

According to Marra [7], there are five steps of adhesive formation in wood substance; flow, transfer, penetration, wetting and solidification. At pressing time of two minutes, there is not enough time for adhesive to solidify enough and achieve good penetration to form a good bonding between porous surfaces of bamboo. However, when the pressing time is increased, higher adhesive shear strength indicating enough time for adhesive to achieve solidification and the penetration to occur to form a good bond line between the bamboo

laminate. This is visually true when inspecting the failure mode and fractured surface of samples. Samples with lower pressing time (2 minutes) exhibit almost 100% failure at adhesive line, implicates that adhesive bond strength is affected by insufficient pressing time.

Adhesives	Time		
	2 mins	5 mins	10 mins
Urea Formaldehyde	3.80 (2.19) ^B	6.13 (1.68) ^A	6.11 (1.46) ^A
Phenol Formaldehyde	4.09 (1.16) ^B	5.36 (1.31) ^A	5.81 (1.62) ^A

Table 3: Average shear strength of UF and PF resins at different pressing time. Values in parentheses are standard deviations.

*Values in the same line that do not share a letter is significantly different

Note: Total number of specimens = 142

A

B

Figure 3: Fractured surface of bamboo pressed for 2 minutes (A) and 10 minutes (B). Noted the shearing of bamboo vascular bundles in (B)

Figure 4: Schematic representation of an adhesive joint, showing various “chain” in the chain analogy as suggested by Marra [8].

8 & 9 are bulk wood, 6 & 7 are wood interphase, 4 & 5 are wood-adhesive interphase, 2 & 3 are adhesive interphase and 1 is bulk adhesive

However, samples with higher pressing time (5 and 10 minutes) exhibits almost 100% bamboo failure, indicating excellent adhesive bonding between the bamboo surface due to

sufficient time for good penetration time and solidification of adhesive to occur. Figure 3 shows the failure mode and fractured surface of samples. Marra has considered a hypothetical

model of adhesive and boundary chain as shown in figure 4. Marra also indicated that the most likely failure zones were the adhesive interphase and wood interphase [7]. Resins bonding in bamboo-bamboo laminate can be considered as nine chain model. At boundary layer (6 & 7), of two bamboo adherend, the properties of the link in this boundary can be altered during sample preparation such as increasing pressing time. Factors such as inadequate curing temperature and too short pressing time may cause the bamboo laminate to fail in the adhesive bond line, resulting to low shear strength.

5 Conclusion

From the experiment, it is found that the adhesive bond strength for both UF and PF resins is found to be satisfactory to provide good adhesive bonding between bamboo laminate. Adhesive bonding strength is greatly affected by pressing time. Too short pressing time is insufficient as good adhesive penetration and solidification may not properly occurred thus affecting adhesive bonding strength. For UF resins, it is found that pressing time of 5 minutes is sufficient to provide good adhesive strength for gluelines in bamboo while for PF resins; longer pressing time (10 minutes) is needed for good adhesive strength for gluelines in bamboo.

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